

A comparison of the educational and sociological backgrounds of 19 low-publishing and 6 high-publishing rice breeders in Asia. Taken from a sample of 38 rice breeders at 27 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Characteristic	Rice breeders	
	Low publishers (19)	High publishers (6)
Highest educational attainment		
B.S. (70)	35	0
M.S. (%)	35	0
Ph.D. (%)	30	100
Source of highest degree		
Local (%)	70	33
Other Asian countries (76)	5	17
Highly developed country (70)	25 ^a	50
Av. age (yr)	40.5	43.8
Av. professional experience (yr)	12.2	15.5
Travel ^b		
Foreign travel (70)	79	83
Trips (av. no./scientist)	2.3	1.5
Preferences for scientific publication ^c		
National (%)	42	17
International (76)	10	0
Highly developed country (76)	32	83
No response (%)	16	0

^a Of six low-publishing Ph.D.'s, four were educated in highly developed nations. One scientist whose highest educational attainment was an M.S. degree had received the degree in a highly developed nation.

^b Scientists who had traveled abroad in the past 5 years.

^c When asked to name the scientific journal or publication in which they would most like to publish an article about their research results, if they could be assured of publication anywhere in the world.

They averaged slightly fewer trips abroad.

The purpose of the research was to better understand how scientific information moves among Asian rice improvement programs. The author in no way implies that the rice breeders who

published the most papers, or even papers in the most prestigious journals, are better or worse scientists than the others.

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Cult. 3885, Cult. 3948. Cult. 3965, Cult. 3964, Cult. 3868, Cult. 5996, Cult. 4295, Cult. 4078, Cult. 3904, Cult. 3900, Cult. 6001, and Cult. 3872.

The moderately resistant rices were: Cult. 3953, Cult. 3916, Cult. 3961, Cult. 3886, Cult. 5994, Cult. 6003, Cult. 3867, Cult. 6008, Cult. 3945, Cult. 3877, Cult. 3987, Cult. 4116, Cult. 13493, CR-1014, Jaya, Bala, IR5, CR-6, Cauvery, Bhavani, Pankaj, Jarnuna, IET-1991, CO2, C07, COI9, C022, GEB24, C027, C028, C023, C031, C032, C036, ADT13, ADT25, ASD4, ASD9, ASD13, ASD7, PTBI5, Tetep, Zenith, Dawn, 46-Palman, IR3273, IR1103-15-8-3, IR1614-389-3, IR579-126, IET2913, V-11/3, V-238, Cult. 2226, Cult. 1900, AC82, Thangasamba, T-336, MTU-5715, F13-22, V12, V121, T215, T1157, T347, Mottai Karu, AC-2959, Jagannath, and Malagkit Sungsong. □

Rice ragged stunt disease in India

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Ragged stunt, a new virus disease of rice, was observed at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, India, in February 1978.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance of rice to sheath blight

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Rice varieties and cultures in Tamil Nadu were screened for resistance to sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. During the maximum-tillering stage, 1,404 cultivars were

inoculated with the *R. solani* pathogen by the straw bit method. Thirty-six rices were resistant and 68 moderately resistant.

The resistant rices were: ADT 22, ADT 5, CO20, Ponni, Ratna, Thillainayagam (S.AR) Cult. 55-100, V228, W449, Wase Aikoku, T1185, V42, Dular, Cult. 2100, Cult. 6547, Cult. 2210-2, Cult. 5143, Kam Ban Ngan, IR1544-340, DGWG, IR1156-501-P, Cult. 3879, Cult. 3896, Cult. 3875,

Percentage of hills infected by ragged stunt virus disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Infected hills ^a (%)
Cult. 644	89
IR30	83
Cult. 1722	83
Cult. 5202	14
IR28	73
Cult. 2361	13
Cult. 2684	69
Cauvery	64
IET2222	63
Cult. 13613	62
Cult. 658	52
IET1444	44
Cult. 1893	43
Vaigai	42
IR36	35

^aMean of 4 replications.

The diseased plants were stunted; leaves were ragged and smaller than normal ones; and flag leaves were deformed. Severely infected plants did not produce healthy grains and had

incomplete panicle emergence. Yield losses ranged from 80 to 100%. Dr. E. A. Heinrichs of IRRI identified the disease in the field as caused by ragged stunt virus.

Ragged stunt incidence was further noted in 17 cultures grown in the field at that time. The percentage of ragged stunt-infected hills is presented in the table. □

Varietal resistance to neck blast in rice

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Blast *Pyricularia oryzae* is one of the most damaging rice diseases in the hills of Uttar Pradesh, India. During kharif 1977, two coordinated Uniform Variety Trials of

rice were conducted at the Rice Research Station, Majhera, Nainital district. Severe neck blast incidence was scored on a scale of 1 to 9. Only 5 entries were resistant (see table). China 988 and China 1039, which have high cold tolerance, were highly susceptible to neck blast. The observations point out a major weakness in the composition of the hill trials. The entries should be thoroughly screened against diseases before promotion to advanced yield

trials. This is particularly necessary in the Uttar Pradesh hills, where all representative races of the pathogen have been reported. □

Reaction of varieties to neck blast in the field. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Reaction ^a	Entries (no.)	Designation
Resistant	5	K17-9-1-1, K30-82-B-1, K35-67-2-1-3-1, K42-115-1-2-1-2, R × T 42.
Moderately resistant	5	K21-9-10-1, K26-2-36, K28-1, K42-86-B-2-1, KH6159.
Susceptible to highly susceptible	23	K17-BK-1-3-1, K18-6-B-2-1-2, K28-KH74, K28-48-B-2, K31-163-3, K39-96-3-1-1-1-2, K41-146-1, K41-105-2, K42-15-1-1-3-3, K46-15-13-2-24-1-1, K46-15-B-2-1, K84, K102-51-10, K102-42-2-1, K143-17-3, K178, K229-59, KR17254, KH7164, China972, China 988, China 1039, IR579-ES-29.

^aScore of 1-3 = resistant, 5 = moderately resistant, 7-9 = susceptible to highly susceptible.

Field reaction of upland rainfed paddy varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India

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The reactions of a few selected varieties to natural infection by various diseases were tested at selected locations during kharif 1977. The table shows the variability of the varieties' reactions to different diseases at different locations, under irrigated and rainfed conditions. □

Reactions of upland paddy varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India.

Designation	Origin	Reaction to diseases ^a at									
		Mandya		Hebbal			Ponnampet				
		LB	NB	LB	NB	BB	BLS	LB	NB	Rhy	Hel
M161	Sel. from Mugad (local)	-	S	-	-	M	-	-	-	M	M
M249	-do-	L	S	M	S	S	M	M	S	M	M
M141	-do-	-	-	M	-	S	M	M	-	-	M
M81	-do-	L	S	-	S	M	L	M	S	-	M
HY258-1	280-51-36/M141	-	M	L	S	M	-	S	S	M	M
HY449-17	M141/Y-4	-	S	L	S	S	L	S	-	-	M
HY26-10	M141/Y-4	L	M	-	S	M	M	S	-	-	M
HY256	A200/475-36	L	M	L	S	S	L	S	S	M	-
HY249-13-1	280-51-36/M-141	L	M	-	S	M	L	S	S	-	M
Waner 1	Sel. from Waner	-	M	M	S	M	M	M	S	S	S
K44-1	Sel. from Kagasal	-	L	-	M	M	L	S	S	-	-
D6-2-2	Sel. from Dodigya	L	-	-	-	S	L	M	M	M	M
Y4	Sel. from Yelikerisal	-	-	-	-	M	M	S	M	-	M
A200	Sel. from Antarsal	M	-	-	-	M	M	S	M	-	-
A67	-do-	-	-	-	-	M	M	M	M	-	M
A90	-do-	L	M	-	S	M	L	M	M	-	S

^aLB = leaf blast, NB = neck blast, BB = bacterial blight, BLS = bacterial leaf streak, Rhy = Rhynchosporium, Hel = Helminthosporium, L = low disease rating, M = medium disease rating, S = severe disease rating.